

Sample 30a

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0000
	{Si}	90.4
	{Al, Si}	4.7
	{Al, Si, K}	2.1
	{Ca}	0.7
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.5
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{Si, Ca LoP}	0.3
	{Na, Si}	0.3
	{Fe}	0.3
	{Si, Ca HiP}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Si}	0.0
	{Al}	0.0
	{S}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.0
	{Mg, Ca}	0.0
	{Mg}	0.0
	{Ca, Fe}	0.0
	{Si, Fe}	0.0
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.0
	{Si, P}	0.0
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{Zn-LA1}	0.0
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.0
	{Ti}	0.0
	{Al, Si, S}	0.0
	{Mg, Fe}	0.0
	{Al, Ca}	0.0
	{S, Ca}	0.0
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.0
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	16.2
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.0
Carbon rich - other	2.3
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	0.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	81.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	0.4
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.0
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.1
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	16.2
Site - carbon-rich other	0.0
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	2.3
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	0.0
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	81.0
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	0.4
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 30b

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0025
	{Si}	84.3
	{Al, Si}	3.6
	{Al, Si, K}	2.8
	{S, Ca}	2.1
	{Fe}	1.3
	{Si, Ca LoP}	0.8
	{Ca}	0.8
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Si, K}	0.6
	{Al}	0.4
	{Si, Ca HiP}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Si}	0.1
	{Na, Si}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Ti, Fe}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{Na, Al}	0.0
	{Ca, Fe}	0.0
	{Al, Ca}	0.0
	{P}	0.0
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.0
	{Cl}	0.0
	{Ti}	0.0
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.0
	{Si, Fe}	0.0
	{Mg}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.2
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	24.6
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.2
Carbon rich - other	1.5
Cement or BOF converter	0.9
Cement	1.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	2.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	66.2
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	2.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.2
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	0.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	24.6
Site - carbon-rich other	0.2
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	1.5
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.9
Urban	3.4
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	66.2
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	2.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 30c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0097
	{Si}	78.8
	{Al, Si}	5.8
	{Ca}	2.4
	{Fe}	2.2
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.0
	{Al, Si, K}	1.7
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.5
	{Si, Ca HiP}	0.9
	{Al}	0.7
	{S, Ca}	0.6
	{Si, K}	0.6
	{Na, Si}	0.5
	{Si, Fe}	0.4
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Si}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Mn}	0.1
	{Al, S}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.0
	{S}	0.0
	{Ti}	0.0
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{Cr, Fe}	0.0
	{Si, Cl}	0.0
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.0
	{P, Ca}	0.0
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.0
	{Cl}	0.0
	{Al, Si, S}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.9
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.4
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.1
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.5
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.1
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	21.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.3
Carbon rich - other	1.7
Cement or BOF converter	0.8
Cement	5.8
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.5
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.6
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	65.8
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	0.6
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	1.2
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.5
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.5
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	21.5
Site - carbon-rich other	0.3
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.7
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.8
Urban	6.9
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	65.8
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	0.6
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels